

EXPLORING THE PRINCIPLES OF UBUNTU IN CLASSROOM PRACTICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract

The principles of Ubuntu philosophy could cultivate and restore African indigenous values and cultures in diverse educational settings. We draw from literature to position Ubuntu pedagogy within classroom practices. As a transformative approach, Ubuntu pedagogy, when embraced with the understanding and dignity it deserves, has a potential not only for reconnecting students with their indigenous values, heritage and cultures, but it also has a capacity to cultivate Ubuntu social values of solidarity, co-existence, respect and cooperation among students. We recommend Ubuntu pedagogy as a transformative and decolonial approach that promotes inclusion and social justice. The paper aims to provide the principles of Ubuntu that guide the possible and effective implementation of Ubuntu pedagogy in diverse classroom settings and implications for practice. The paper contributes to the ongoing debates on the decolonisation of education and the role of Ubuntu philosophy in the restoration of African values in the classroom practices.

Keywords: African indigenous, classroom practice, decolonisation of education, Ubuntu pedagogy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ubuntu is one such principle of our indigenous inheritance that could make a significant contribution to education if given a chance. In the classroom practices, Ubuntu could help lecturers to create and maintain a conducive learning environment that is favourable and supportive for all students for an effective teaching and learning process to take place. The observations by Lickona (1996, cited in Lewis 2001) are the antithesis of the values of Ubuntu. The classroom practice is perceived to be an appropriate environment in which to teach pertinent morals and values to students, although the researcher is cognisant of the fact that teaching values and morals should be a shared responsibility between parents and lecturers. However, lecturers are well placed to inculcate such values since students spend most of their time at the university with lecturers who have a greater or lesser influence on the students. In African culture the community always comes first (Venter 2004). The individual is born out of and into the community; therefore they will always be part of the community. The lecturer therefore has a responsibility to build a sense of community in the classroom practise which is based on collective responsibility. In a classroom practice that is based on Ubuntu principles learning takes place through interactions with others, students are nurtured and developed in order for them to construct knowledge and acquire skills, values, and attitudes in the classroom through cooperation and taking responsibility for one another's success. The lecturer encourages and establishes student self-control through a process of promoting positive student achievement. This paper argues that for

any classroom to succeed, it must embrace the values of Ubuntu which include humanness, compassion, cooperation, caring, sharing, respect, honesty and humility amongst the students and the lecturer.

2. UBUNTU PEDAGOGY

The concept of Ubuntu pedagogy is defined as “a humanising approach to teaching and engaging students in the learning process” (Blackwood, 2018: 30). Lecturers embracing Ubuntu pedagogy create a learning space that “affirms, validates, and treats students as dignified human beings regardless of their race or class” (Ukpokodu 2016: 155). “A student-centred pedagogical approach that promotes democratic atmospheres where students feel respected, cared for and have the freedom to co-learn in an environment where power relations are grounded in humanism” (Ukpokodu 2016: 155). Central to Ubuntu pedagogy is the idea that all students, irrespective of their racial, educational, economic, and linguistic backgrounds and sexual orientations are humans, who are capable of excelling in their learning if their humanity is positioned at the forefront of their teaching and learning. That is, Ubuntu pedagogy asserts students as significant others who bring unique backgrounds, experiences, and prior knowledge for lecturers to build on towards the development of new knowledge. In that way, lecturers need students’ contributions to create a meaningful learning space. One is not complete without the other. Hence, the essence of Ubuntu pedagogy lies in the recognition of equal partnership between the lecturers and students as co-creators of knowledge. Thus, the Ubuntu maxim ‘motho ke motho ka batho’ (a person is a person through other people) comes into full blossom in the classroom (Letseka 2000:335). When lecturers understand and embrace Ubuntu, it is likely that Ubuntu values can empower them to combat exclusion and employ pedagogies that aim to reach all students in the classrooms. Inclusive pedagogies thrive on the connectedness between students, lecturers, and a community of learning, which all provide a positive environment, which in turn positively influences students’ self-worth, self-belief, and achievement. Successful learning depends on these networks of support. Phasha (2016: 4) argues that inclusive education is the essence of Ubuntu – that we live in a delicate web of interconnectedness and interdependence with each other: ‘I am because we are’ (Phasha 2016:4). Inclusive pedagogy, like Ubuntu, has the potential to promote respect, cooperation and solidarity among students and lecturers. In this way, all students feel a sense of belonging and acceptance. Ubuntu in education is African cultural capitals that provide indigenous knowledge which is important for integrating into our African conception of inclusion which in turn promote inclusivity (Letseka 2013: 148). In other words, Ubuntu pedagogy does not only encourage the development of all students as individuals, but it also promotes active collaboration between students from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds who bring different characteristics and learning needs into the classrooms. In this way, Ubuntu pedagogy affirms diversity as an ordinary aspect of development. Ubuntu pedagogy rejects exclusion, marginalisation and inequality in the teaching and learning spaces (Phasha 2016:5). and language. Lecturers practising within Ubuntu perspectives provide all students, irrespective of their cultural, linguistic, social class, religion, and sexual orientations, with equal opportunities to develop and to exercise their full capacities (Letseka 2013:335). Where Ubuntu pedagogy and social justice exist in a classroom, all students are treated with dignity and respect regardless of their backgrounds. “The value of Ubuntu is to make the relationship between learners and break down the barriers of diversity within the classroom settings. These are also goals of social justice in education” (Broodryk 2005: 46). Ubuntu encompasses values of social justice and promotes relationships between students, breaking down barriers and stereotypes regarding race, gender, ability, language, and culture. For lecturers and HEI to fully practise social justice, they should first be influenced by Ubuntu values. Ubuntu, therefore, can be regarded as a weapon that can be used by lectures to challenge inequity and injustices (Nxumalo & Mncube 2019:107).

Ubuntu pedagogy as a transformative approach is anchored by five principles which underpin and guide its possible and effective implementation as a transformative pedagogical strategy in diverse educational settings: 1. understanding self and others; 2. building positive relationships; 3. getting the class to work together; 4. nurturing the minds of the students; 5 acknowledgement of students’ diverse languages (Ukpokodu 2016:155).

- Understanding self and others Through participation and interactions humans develop identity and belonging. From an African perspective, teaching and learning suggests that it is through engagement with other people that a person grows more fully human, more truly in their identity. In other words, through participation and interaction with others we see ourselves – ‘I participate, therefore I am’ (Tutu 2000). I see myself through others, therefore I belong. Ubuntu pedagogy, therefore, places value on collective learning through interactions and participation. students understand more of what they know or do not know through interactions with others. Active learning through participation, interactions, sharing of ideas, knowledge and

experiences promotes effective learning. Equally, understanding of self and others is critical in a learning process. If you understand yourself, you know your strengths and accept your weaknesses. If you understand others, you also understand their strengths and weaknesses. A learning process therefore becomes an interdependent and a mutual activity (Ukpokodu 2016:154).

- Building a positive relationship, A second principle of Ubuntu pedagogy is building a positive relationship. It is this principle of Ubuntu pedagogy that is responsible for peace and harmonious learning environments where students respect one another and their lecturers as adults within the learning context. Effective learning cannot take place unless students, love one another, respect each other as individuals and human beings. Love for one another creates a positive learning atmosphere among learners. Love brings care for another, sympathy, forgiveness, sharing and peace in the classroom. Love among students ensures that they share not only knowledge, but they also share learning tools and learning spaces with one another. Love promotes respect among students and lecturers, and this leads to positive relations in the classroom (Ukpokodu 2016:154). Respect also entails that learners treat one another with dignity. They respect each other's ideas and experiences even though they differ from their own. When learners love and respect each other, there are high chances that they will listen to one another's ideas and thoughts. Respect is an essential principle of Ubuntu philosophy and way of life, and it guides teaching and learning; it leads to positive relationships and harmony among individuals. Teaching and learning anchored by Ubuntu brings about kindness, caring, togetherness, solidarity, cooperation and sharing among learners and teachers, which all promote positive relationships (Ukpokodu 2016:154).

- Working together and cooperatively Working together is another important principle of Ubuntu pedagogy. It promotes unity and team spirit among students as they tackle learning problems. Unity ensures solidarity, oneness among group members. In such a learning environment, students value one another, and they cease to see one another as competitors, but see them as team members, and extensions of the other. In an effective teamwork, each member is important for a successful learning experience. Each member's contribution is important. Working together promotes the Ubuntu notion of 'for I know, so you know' classroom environment where students not only take care of each other's physical needs such as sharing classroom furniture and learning tools, but they also share knowledge, thus extending each other's cognitive development. Supporting one another is a vital component of Ubuntu pedagogy. In an African Ubuntu perspective, sharing knowledge means I give you what I know, I am giving you what I have so that you can also have, because tomorrow I will also need your help. Therefore, Ubuntu pedagogy ensures that students work together and help one another to learn and understand the learning material. This what Vygotsky (1978:105) calls a socio-cultural environment which builds on peer support scaffolding for effective learning opportunities. Scaffolding refers to carefully designed activities by which the knowledgeable peers support struggling peers until they can independently carry the task without any support, by which they reach a level of proximal development (ZPD). However, where there is a lack of Ubuntu, humanity, there is little help and care for another person. There is little support among learners, as each learner learns for himself or herself. This way of learning is mostly prominent in the Western education system which promotes individualistic and competitive learning. In such learning environments, weak learners remain weak and strong learners continue to achieve and shine. In contrast, Ubuntu pedagogy draws from an African communal way of living and sharing where people share their blessings with those who have little or none. When you have knowledge, you share it with others. In essence, when learners work together, they achieve more than they could when they worked as individuals. That is the principle of Ubuntu pedagogy (Ukpokodu 2016:154).

- Nurturing of students' minds Another important element of Ubuntu pedagogy is the nurturing of students' minds. Ubuntu pedagogy prioritises participative and interactive learning. students learn best when they interact with their ideas, thoughts, and experiences with each other. Interaction on the learning material maximises participation. Actively learning promotes engagement with the learning materials. Students get opportunities to discuss the problems, to ask questions, to debate on concepts and to share their thinking and experiences. Such classrooms foster cognitive development among students. They nurture students' minds and expand their learning opportunities (Ukpokodu 2016:155).

- Acknowledgement of students' diverse languages of students' diverse languages for meaningful learning and teaching in multilingual classrooms. Accepting, respecting, and embracing students' diverse linguistic resources does not only enhance their learning; it also restores identity and dignity. It is through their languages that students can make sense of the world and reflect meaningfully. Embracing students' home languages alongside the language of teaching and learning restores students' identity and the dignity of their cultural languages. Besides, Makelela (2014:188) feels that it is time that boundaries that isolate and

separate languages are broken so all languages that students bring to the classrooms could be used for enhancing students' learning. Multilingual practices such as translanguaging enables teachers and students to draw from different linguistic repertoires for meaningful and purposeful learning. However, successful multilingual practices such as translanguaging require that lecturers accept and recognise all languages spoken by students as equal. Linguistic equality means that no language is viewed as superior to other languages in the classroom (Makalela 2016:188). Ubuntu pedagogy: Implications for practice It has been argued in this paper that the colonial education system has socialised African students out of their indigenous beliefs and knowledge systems. They no longer remember who they are. They have lost their values and identity. On the other hand, this paper has also argued that teaching and learning from an African perspective, that is rich in cultural practices such as Ubuntu, have the potential to preserve indigenous knowledge systems and practices among students and restore their identities. This implies that lecturers, especially those teaching in the post-colonial and decolonial educational settings, should draw from Ubuntu pedagogy to provide students with environments in which they can actively engage with others because it is through participation and interaction with others that students understand themselves and others and grow more fully human, more truly in their identity (Muwanga-Zake 2009:413). Pedagogies that build from Ubuntu philosophy promote cooperation among students. Such classrooms instil in students the communal values so that they learn and embrace the spirit of sharing. Students learn that if you have knowledge, you share it with others. They begin to appreciate that when they work together, they achieve more than they could when they work as individuals. As such, Ubuntu pedagogy thrives on positive relationships among students, which yields respect, love for one another, sympathy and sharing of learning resources and knowledge. Lecturers utilising Ubuntu pedagogy promote respect among students and this entails that students treat each other with dignity.

They embrace and respect each other's ideas and experiences even though they may differ from their own. Teaching anchored in the values of Ubuntu creates positive learning atmospheres among students and lecturers and promotes social cohesion (Ukpokodu 2016:154). In South Africa many students in educational institutions are African students. Strangely enough, they learn through a foreign and colonial language, English, while their indigenous languages remain marginalised. Teaching and learning grounded on Ubuntu philosophical principles respects and restores dignity to students' heritages, including their languages. Ubuntu pedagogy enables teachers to recognise and utilise students' linguistic resources to create meaningful learning experiences.

3. UBUNTU - CURRICULUM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Ubuntu and curriculum policy documents Department of Education (DoE). (2002) National curriculum Statement (NCS) and Curriculum assessment policy statement (CAPS) have the impact and principles that link or reveal Ubuntu in them. The whole education process centres around Ubuntu as a philosophy of principles that capture the belief system of the South Africans according to which people take responsibility to others and accept the authority and guidance of others to progress. The concept of Ubuntu is also understood indirectly through the inclusivity in education and society; the constitution of republic of South Africa (Act 108 of 1996) states founded our democratic state and common citizenship on the values of human dignity, the achievement of equality and the advancement of human rights and freedoms that Education White Paper 6: (2011), states In this regard, Ubuntu, and curriculum policy documents Department of Education (DoE). (2002) National curriculum Statement (NCS) and Curriculum assessment policy statement (CAPS) have values, that link or reveal Ubuntu in them. These values summon all of us to take up the responsibility and challenge of building a humane and caring society for everyone which also emphasize the concept of Ubuntu with the society by including everyone within the society. The white paper 6 of inclusive education reveal the indirect understanding of Ubuntu, the white paper 6 understand Ubuntu as acknowledging the fact that learners and students could learn, accept, and respect the fact that all students are different in some way and have different learning needs which are equally valued. Institutional development will therefore focus on assisting higher education institutions to recognise and address the diverse range of learning needs among students. White Paper 6: (2011), states that lecturers should acknowledge and respect differences in students, whether due to age, gender, ethnicity, language, class, disability or HIV status, the principles from white paper 6 of inclusive education contain the values of Ubuntu and is actual revealing Ubuntu indirectly.(white paper 6 Special need education:2011) also emphasize the values of Ubuntu by respecting others difference and including them in the education system. Both curriculum documents ensure that students acquire and apply knowledge and the skills in a meaningful way to their lives. Social transformation ensures the educational imbalances of the past are readdressed and equal educational opportunities are provided for every individual, that principle also support or link with one

of social justice goal which is equality. The second purpose of NCS is also somehow fulfilling the Ubuntu values which emphasize the active and critical learning that encourage active learning approach. The principle stated by curriculum documents; equality, kindness, and other human rights equality, inclusivity environmental and social justice, infusing principles and practices human rights, all the stated principles are the core values of Ubuntu and others are social justice goals, others such as inclusivity are also contained in white paper 6 which support the humanness. The purpose of the curriculum documents supports the fact of inclusivity in education which is one of core value of Ubuntu; says students would be equipped irrespective of their socio- economic background, race, gender, physical ability, intellectual ability with knowledge and values necessary for self-fulfilment and meaning of participation in society.

4. UBUNTU- WORKING AS A COLLECTIVE

Students in HEI acknowledged the role of Ubuntu philosophy's pillars of solidarity, cooperation, respect, caring and kindness as a driving force and motivation for sharing ideas, resources, and skills during classroom practices. Ubuntu provides a strong philosophical base for the community, and HEI should be viewed as a community. The principle of solidarity thrives on unity, unconditional love and respect for one another, mutual interest for collective survival and responsibility towards fellow members as opposed to selfishness and competitiveness towards or among African community members. In the same way, Muwanga-Zake (2009: 415) claims that "the spirit of solidarity is best epitomised by a metaphor that "one finger cannot crush a grain of wheat on its own, it needs the help of the other four fingers". In other words, the ability of humans to interdependently pull together in a 'one for all and all for one' spirit, is the value of solidarity. Coexistence is another core principle of Ubuntu philosophy. This is the ability to live with others (co-exist) in harmony. What students learn in their classroom practices, when it comes to interactions with those who are different from them translates into how well they will manage life in the global marketplace. According to the evidence on the emphasise of the well-developed multicultural curriculum, is very important, since it is the integration of ideals into HEI courses of study that nurture the practice that hopes to transform the ways in which students are instructed by giving equal attention to the contributions of all groups in a society. Multicultural education cannot be taught in a textbook, it must be developed by each lecturer based on a particular student group. Lecturers could help students discover their academic strength by helping them discover their own learning style. Multicultural curriculum helps students understand the significant historical experiences and basic cultural patterns of ethnic groups, the critical contemporary issues and social problems confronting each of them, and the dynamic diversity of the experiences, cultures, and individuals within each ethnic group. Thus, Ubuntu philosophy can cultivate and restore African indigenous values and cultures and transform educational practices in diverse South African classrooms practices.

5. UBUNTU - INDIGENOUS VALUE

Ubuntu philosophy, which is indigenous to African people, when embraced with the understanding and dignity it deserves, has the potential not only of reconnecting students in the South African education system with their indigenous values, heritage, and cultures, but Ubuntu philosophy has a capacity to promote co-existence, social cohesion, and inclusivity among students from diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds. A deeper understanding of Ubuntu philosophy and its principles is essential to maintaining its cultural integrity if it is to be incorporated into the education system. Mbigi's (1997) Collective Fingers Theory to bring forth the principles guiding Ubuntu philosophy, which drive the cultivation and promotion of values of solidarity, cooperation, respect, inclusivity, and social cohesion.

It is surprising that a culturally rich indigenous practice such as Ubuntu remains overlooked and neglected in educational spaces, especially those located in Africa and, specifically, in South Africa. Mucina (2013:19) notes that many African institutions continue to function from the Western, Eurocentric view which undermines and dismisses indigenous philosophies such as Ubuntu as false assumptions and simple illegitimate African thinking. This rejection of the Ubuntu philosophy could be the main reason why it has not filtered through to education systems and curricula in many African countries, including South Africa (Maphalala 2017:10237). MuwangaZake (2009:413) posits that colonial education systems and their assumption of Western philosophical world views as superior knowledge have socialised Africans, especially the youth, out of their indigenous beliefs and knowledge systems and given them a false 'global view' of who they are. Indigenous knowledge and pedagogies have almost vanished among young people, their existence confined to distant memories. African people, especially the youth, no longer remember who they were and who they are (Muwanga-Zake 2009:413). Meanwhile, South African scholars like Hlatshwayo, Shawa & Nxumalo (2020:4) have noticed that students in South Africa grow up with incorrect information and

knowledge about their indigenous heritage and ethnic values like Ubuntu because the school curriculum and pedagogies lack African philosophy such as Ubuntu. Students have lost their African values and identity. Another South African scholar, Letseka (2013:334), adds that the education system in South Africa cannot continue to turn a blind eye to the local indigenous knowledge systems such as Ubuntu philosophy that has guided the way of life of the African people for centuries. There is no complete transformation and decolonisation of education in South Africa without restoration and recognition of indigenous heritages of the African people (Letseka 2013:335).

6. UBUNTU- THE AFRICAN CULTURE

For African cultures, the principle of compassion comes first as it naturally permits other values of cooperation, solidarity, and co-existence. Co-existence thrives on mutual interdependence among members of the group, cooperation, and mutual respect. In relation to coexistence, Ubuntu is more concerned with the fact that as human beings we cannot exist isolation. Ubuntu speaks to interconnectedness ... We think of ourselves far too frequently as just individuals, separated from one another, whereas we are connected and what we do affects the existence of the group" (Tutu 2000:22). Where there is Ubuntu, there is respect and peace. There is equality among members of the community. Coexistence entails that there is acceptance and respect of diversity. This includes accepting and respecting other people's opinions and ideas that differ from yours. Coexistence flourishes where students embrace cooperation and mutual learning goals. Du Toit, Poovan and Engelbretch (2006: 19) assert that "Humans' ability to understand others' dilemmas and challenges is compassion." According to these scholars, compassion promotes feelings of belonging and interconnectedness observed in African communities. Compassion is probably one of the most important principles of Ubuntu philosophy and the indigenous African way of life. It is a sense and feeling of care, sympathy and concern for another person which becomes evident through helping another human being, sharing, and showing sympathy towards others. Showing kindness through sharing and sympathy towards another human being is important in African cultures. Sharing what you have with another is confirmation of belonging and brotherhood in African cultures. Compassion inspires love and caring for one another and motivates feelings of 'I cannot have all while you have nothing, let us share'. In other words, compassion holds members of the cultural communities together and strengthens bonds of togetherness and solidarity. It helps to maintain positive relationships (Mbigi 1997:32. Poovan (2005:25) argues that Ubuntu values of respect and dignity are the fundamental social values in the African cultures. "It is only through respecting others with dignity that one gains others respect and trust" (Poovan 2005: 25). Respect played a vital role among African indigenous cultural people. It promoted harmony and peace: interpersonal relationships should be managed based on unconditional acceptance and positive regard. Unconditional respect is the basis of effective communism, positive relations, effective cooperation, and harmonious co-existence (Poovan 2005: 25). Mutual respect among members is therefore crucial, as it yields a positive cultural climate and sustains the Ubuntu values of co-existence, cooperation and solidarity among people.

7. CONCLUSION

In higher education institution (HEI), teaching from a position of love and care is almost impossible to speak of Ubuntu without referring to acts of humanity such as love, kindness, sympathy and respect and solidarity. Teaching from a position of love does not only empower students in the classroom, but it also sparks a change for the better in students, no matter what the situation is (Blackwood 2018:30). A classroom is a place that enables teachers to show love and care for their students through helping them to develop cognitively and holistically. Lecturers' love helps students to persevere in times of academic challenges. It pushes students to try again and again in times of challenges. A teacher's love motivates students to see themselves as achievers. Lecturers who teach from the perspective of love and care can embrace their students' diverse personalities, their strengths and weaknesses in the classroom (Blackwood 2018:30). Such lecturers never doubt the potential and capabilities of their students. Instead, they help students grow beyond their intellectual abilities. A classroom that is centred on a lecturer's love towards students and among students is nurturing and supportive. Students are motivated to help one another overcome learning barriers. They are encouraged to be cooperative and to be kind towards others' learning challenges. In that way, students become willing to learn together and share information. Education without love becomes a mere ideology (Blackwood 2018:30). Lecturers may use expected teaching strategies and techniques, but if teachers lack love for the students and for the teaching, such efforts fail to inspire students. If good strategies are used by an unloving lecturer who spends more time consciously or unconsciously speaking and acting in contrary to love, this may disempower students and they may lose respect for their lectures. That is, teaching that truly inspires and empowers students does not come only from good strategies and a perfect curriculum,

but it is the pedagogy that is love-centred. A teacher's love makes a difference in the presence of effective teaching tools and strategies. Without a loving and inspirational lecturer in the classroom, subjects and learning can be boring and irrelevant. Loving lecturers trigger an experience of love, respect and caring from the students in the way they speak to students and in the way they treat all their students irrespective of race, gender, cultural backgrounds, academic abilities, and physical abilities. "As one develops towards love, one is capable of loving oneself holistically, and because of this holistic love of oneself love, one can love the world holistically" (Blackwood 2018:30). The more students spend time with loving lecturers, the more they experience love and the more they become eager to transfer love to others in the classroom. A transformative teaching approach that can foster understanding of self and others among students, build positive relationships encourage cooperation and respect among students inspire teachers to teach from a position of love and care and promote inclusion and social justice.

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